

URSSI Conceptualization Community Survey

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This document contains the survey questions from a community survey conducted as part of the conceptualization of a United States Research Software Sustainability Institute (<http://URSSI.us>) funded by the United States National Science Foundation SI2 Institutes program.

The goal of this survey is to better understand research software user and developer communities in the United States. The focus of the survey was to gather information to help identify how to increase the sustainability of research software. To gather a broad range of perspectives, we distributed the survey to 25,000 NSF and 25,000 NIH PIs whose projects involve research software, as well as to mailing lists of interested people such as the WSSSPE email list. In addition, we used snowballing by asking people to forward the survey to others who might be interested.

CONSENT

Consent to Participate in Internet Research

Identification of Investigator and Purpose of Study: You are invited to participate in a research study, entitled “S2I2 Conceptualization: URSSI: Conceptualizing a US Research Software Sustainability Institute.” The study is being conducted by a multi-institutional team of scholars, including Kate E. Mueller, J.D. of the Center for Social Research at the University of Notre Dame, kate.mueller@nd.edu, and Sandra Gesing, Ph.D., Research Assistant Professor of Computer Science and Engineering at the University of Notre Dame, sgesing@nd.edu.

The purpose of this research study is to assess the needs of the research software development and user community on best practices of the sustainable development of research software. Your participation in the study will contribute to a better understanding of the development and use of research software. You are free to contact the investigator at the above email address to discuss the study. You must be at least 18 years old to participate.

If you agree to participate: The survey will evaluate your development and/or use of research software and will take approximately 10-15 minutes of your time. You will not be compensated.

Risks/Benefits/Confidentiality of Data: There are no known risks. There will be no costs for participating, nor will you directly benefit, though you may indirectly benefit as a member of the research software development and user community. Your response will be anonymous and the research team will not collect or connect your response to your name, email address, or IP address.

Participation or Withdrawal: Your participation in this study is voluntary. You may decline to answer any question and you have the right to withdraw from participation at any time. Withdrawal will not affect your relationship with the University of Notre Dame in any way. If you do not want to participate, simply stop participating or close the browser window. If you do not want to receive any more reminders, you may email us at csr@nd.edu.

Contacts: If you have any questions about the study, please contact the research team

at csr@nd.edu. This study has been reviewed and approved by the University of Notre Dame Institutional Review Board as study number 18-08-4802.

Questions about your rights as a research participant: For questions about your rights or any dissatisfaction with any part of this study, you can contact, anonymously if you wish, the Notre Dame Research Compliance Office, at 574-631-1461 or by email at compliance@nd.edu.

You may print a copy of this document for your records

If you agree to participate, please click the arrow below to proceed to the survey.

Profile

Which profile matches the work you perform?

Researchers (pure user)

- I primarily use software to do my research.
- I have contributed to local software development, but only in a limited capacity.
- I have the ability to recognize and report bugs.
- I don't build **new** software myself, but I occasionally modify existing software for my own needs.

Developers (pure software developer)

- I primarily write software for others to use.
- I contribute to collaborative software projects
- I maintain a package or distribution

Combination

- I have attributes of both "Researchers" and "Developers"
- I both write software for my own research and write software that other researchers use for their research

Demographics

Demographics

The following questions are for classification purposes.

What type of organization do you work for?

- Educational institution

- National lab
- Industry
- Other

In which country do you currently reside?

What is your professional title?

- Faculty
- Postdoc
- Graduate Student
- Research Engineer
- Research Faculty
- Research Software Engineer
- Manager
- Other

In which discipline(s) do you perform research?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Biological sciences | <input type="checkbox"/> Administrative & business studies |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Mathematical and physical sciences | <input type="checkbox"/> Agricultural |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering | <input type="checkbox"/> Forestry and veterinary science |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Computer & information Science | <input type="checkbox"/> Education |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Medicine | <input type="checkbox"/> Architecture and planning |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Dentistry and health | <input type="checkbox"/> Design |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Social sciences | <input type="checkbox"/> Creative & performing arts |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Humanities and language based studies | |

What is your age?

- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54

- 55 - 64
- 65 - 74
- 75 - 84
- 85 or older

How many years have you worked in research?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 - 5 years
- 6 - 10 years
- 11 - 15 years
- 16-20 years
- More than 20 years

What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

How often do you work on projects that have the following team size?

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
1 person	<input type="radio"/>				
2 - 5 people	<input type="radio"/>				
6 - 20 people	<input type="radio"/>				
More than 20 people	<input type="radio"/>				

Developer_Practices

Software Development Practices

For the following questions, think about your most recently completed software project and answer based on your experiences in that project.

To what extent was the software targeted at each of these groups of users?

	Not at all	Secondary target	Primary target
Just me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Just my team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Just my discipline	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More than one discipline	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What percent of your time did you actually spend in the following activities (total should be 100%)?

Requirements gathering / documentation	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Software architecture / design	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Coding	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Testing	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Debugging	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Maintenance	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Documentation	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Meetings	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Training	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Total	<input type="text" value="0"/>

What percent of time would you have **liked** to have spent in each activity (total should be 100%)?

Requirements gathering / documentation	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Software architecture / design	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Coding	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Testing	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Debugging	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Maintenance	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Documentation	<input type="text" value="0"/>

Meetings	0
Training	0
Other <input type="text"/>	0
Total	0

Which of the following types of testing did you employ?

	Frequently	Somewhat	Rarely	Never
Unit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Integration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
System	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
User	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regression	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Did you release the software under an open-source license?

- Yes
- No

Developer_infrastructure_tools

Development Infrastructure and Tools

The following questions are about software development infrastructure, tools, and practices with which you may use or are familiar.

In the last 5 years, how much experience do you have with each of the following types of projects:

	None	1-3 projects	4+ projects
Single developer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Co-located team (i.e. a team, located in a single place or institution with well-coordinated funding/organization)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	None	1-3 projects	4+ projects
Distributed team (i.e. a well-defined team, located in multiple places or institutions with well-coordinated funding/organization)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open source community (i.e. a group of developers who are distributed and working under multiple independent funding sources)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How well do current tools support each of the following activities?

	Extremely supported	Very supported	Moderately supported	Slightly supported	Not supported at all
Requirements gathering / documentation	<input type="radio"/>				
Software architecture / design	<input type="radio"/>				
Coding	<input type="radio"/>				
Testing	<input type="radio"/>				
Debugging	<input type="radio"/>				
Maintenance	<input type="radio"/>				
Documentation	<input type="radio"/>				

Training

Training

The following questions are aimed to help us understand where developers may have received formal or informal training for software development.

Have you received training for software development?

- Yes
- No

Where?

- Class / school

- Carpentry
- Online self-directed
- Other

Do you believe there are sufficient opportunities available for exploring or obtaining new software skills?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Do you have sufficient time to take the types of training you need to be successful?

- Yes
- No

For each of the following types of training (languages, development techniques, and project management), which mode of delivery do you prefer? Please select your top two modes of delivery preferences for each of the training types.

	Languages	Development Techniques	Project Management
On-site custom training	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Workshops or short courses (e.g., before or after a conference)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Carpentries / software boot camps	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Summer schools (in person or virtual)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
MOOCs (massive open online courses), webinars, or self-directed online courses	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Funding_Institutional_Support

Funding and Institutional Support

The following questions are aimed at understanding your funding and institutional support for research

software activities.

Have you ever included costs for software development in a funding proposal?

- Yes
- No

Select all costs for software development in your funding proposals?

- For developing new software
- For reusing existing software
- For maintaining / sustaining software

What percent of the funding for your software work comes from each of the following?

NSF	<input type="text" value="0"/>
NIH	<input type="text" value="0"/>
DoD	<input type="text" value="0"/>
DoE	<input type="text" value="0"/>
NASA	<input type="text" value="0"/>
NOAA	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Private foundation	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Your own institution (e.g. faculty salary)	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Other <input style="width: 150px;" type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Total	<input style="color: red;" type="text" value="0"/>

Does your institution provide support for your research software development activities in the following ways:

	No	Yes, but inadequate level of support	Yes, adequate level of support
Financial	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructural (repositories, computing, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	No	Yes, but inadequate level of support	Yes, adequate level of support
Consulting / RSE support	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Does your institution provide / support the research software development you need in the following ways:

	No	Yes, but inadequate level of support	Yes, adequate level of support
Financial	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructural (repositories, computing, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consulting / RSE support	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What are the most significant gaps in your current institutional / organizational support of software related research?

Career Paths

Career Paths

The following questions are designed to provide information about career support and career pathways for research software developers.

In your institution, which of the following positions are available for people whose primary role is to develop research software?

- Postdoc
- Research Software Engineer
- Research Programmer
- Software Developer

- Programmer
- Faculty
- Research Faculty
- Other

Is there opportunity for career advancement (e.g., tenure, more senior positions) for people whose primary role is to develop research software at your institution?

- Yes - in my current institution
- No - I would have to move to another institution
- Don't know

With regard to hiring and maintaining a highly qualified software development staff, how important are the following concerns?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Identifying a pipeline for future staff	<input type="radio"/>				
Attracting staff from underrepresented groups (e.g., race, gender, ethnicity, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Availability of staff who can work across disciplines	<input type="radio"/>				
Competing with industry for top performers	<input type="radio"/>				
Offering a viable career path	<input type="radio"/>				
Opportunities to outsource skilled work	<input type="radio"/>				

In your opinion: How important were the following concerns when you were hired into your current position?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Diversity in the organization (e.g., in terms of race, gender, ethnicity)	<input type="radio"/>				
Your experience as programmer or software engineer	<input type="radio"/>				

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Your background in science	<input type="radio"/>				
Your knowledge of diverse programming languages	<input type="radio"/>				
Your knowledge and capabilities across disciplines	<input type="radio"/>				
Your potential for growth	<input type="radio"/>				

Credit for Software Contributions

Credit for Software Contributions

This section elicits information about citation and attribution of research software.

When you write a paper and the work being described uses software, how often do you use each of the following approaches to mention the software?

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
Cite paper about the software	<input type="radio"/>				
Cite the software user's manual	<input type="radio"/>				
Mention the name of the software	<input type="radio"/>				
Mention the URL of the software	<input type="radio"/>				
Cite the URL of the software	<input type="radio"/>				
Cite the published / archived software itself	<input type="radio"/>				
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

How often do you currently receive the following types of credit for your software contributions?

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
(Co)author on research paper	<input type="radio"/>				

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
(Co)author on software paper	<input type="radio"/>				
Acknowledgement in paper	<input type="radio"/>				
Software cited in a paper	<input type="radio"/>				
Funded/hired to work on the software	<input type="radio"/>				
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

For your job role, does your institution allow software contributions to be considered in performance reviews or promotion cases?

- Yes
- No
- Dependent on the position (programmer vs. faculty)

How important do you believe software contributions are for your own performance review or promotion case?

- Not at all important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Very important
- Extremely important

Diversity/Inclusion

Diversity and Inclusion

Please answer the following questions based on the software project you work on most. If the questions do not apply please select N/A.

How well does your project do the following:

	Terrible	Poor	Average	Good	Excellent	N/A
Recruit participants from underrepresented groups	<input type="radio"/>					

	Terrible	Poor	Average	Good	Excellent	N/A
Retain participants from underrepresented groups	<input type="radio"/>					
Include participants from underrepresented groups in governance and leadership positions	<input type="radio"/>					
Maintain a culture of inclusion	<input type="radio"/>					

What are the challenges you face in creating / maintaining a culture of inclusion?

Does your project do any measurement, tracking, or analysis of developer or user communities - with regard to diversity and/or inclusion? If so, please describe below.

Follow Up Selection Block

Thank you for taking time to complete this survey. Are you willing to answer a few more questions about any of the following areas? (Please check all that apply).

- Software Development Practices
- Development Infrastructure and Tools
- Training
- Funding / Institutional Support
- Career Paths
- Credit for Software Contributions
- Diversity / Inclusion

Software Development Practices Follow Up

Maintenance is important for the long-term sustainability of a software project. For the following activities that are considered part of software maintenance, indicate what type of support you need for each activity:

	Training	Guidance	Infrastructure
Planning maintenance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Change tracking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Defect tracking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Porting to new platforms	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Configuration management	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regression testing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Overall, regardless of where you spend the most time, which of the following aspects of software development are more difficult than you think they should be?

- Project management
- Requirements elicitation / engineering
- Finding personnel / Developer turnover
- Communication (among those with different expertise, among different teams)
- Use of best practices vs. need for rapid delivery
- Keeping up with modern tools
- Porting
- Testing
- Debugging
- Other
- None of the above

How often do you employ the following practices when developing software?

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
Requirements gathering	<input type="radio"/>				
Software architecture or design	<input type="radio"/>				
Continuous Integration	<input type="radio"/>				
Pair programming	<input type="radio"/>				
Waterfall	<input type="radio"/>				

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
Rational Unified Process (RUP)	<input type="radio"/>				
Peer code review	<input type="radio"/>				
Coding standards	<input type="radio"/>				

How often do you perform each of the following practices when developing software?

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
Develop a user manual or online help	<input type="radio"/>				
Comment code	<input type="radio"/>				
Use descriptive variables and method names	<input type="radio"/>				

How often do you document the following information when developing software?

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
Software requirements	<input type="radio"/>				
User stories / use cases	<input type="radio"/>				
Software architecture / design decisions	<input type="radio"/>				
Test plan / test goals	<input type="radio"/>				

Development Infrastructure and Tools Follow Up

Do you use use a version control system?

- Yes
 No

How often do you use each of the following for version control systems.

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
Git	<input type="radio"/>				
SVN	<input type="radio"/>				

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
Mercurial	<input type="radio"/>				
Copying files to another location (e.g., a network share or cloud location)	<input type="radio"/>				
Zip file backups	<input type="radio"/>				
Something else <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

On average, how frequently do you check-in or commit code to a version control system?

- After every change
- After a small group of changes
- After a major set of changes
- Never
- Other

Do you use continuous integration?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half the time
- Most of the time
- Always

Training Follow Up

Please list any specific software-related training activities that you have found helpful (either the name, a link, or the topic).

What software-related topics would you or your team like to receive training about?

Funding Institutional Support Follow Up

The following questions are aimed at understanding your current funding for research software activities.

In general, do you think you have sufficient funding to support software development activities in your research?

Sufficient to do my work				Insufficient and creates barrier to my work
<input type="radio"/>	2	3	4	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In particular, how well does your current funding support the following activities?

	Sufficient to do my work	2	3	4	Insufficient and creates barrier to my work
Developing new software	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Modifying or reusing existing software	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Maintaining software	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If you develop new software, does your current funding support the following activities:

	Sufficient to do my work	2	3	4	Insufficient and creates barrier to my work
Refactoring	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Testing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Creating or updating documentation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Responding to issues / bugs reported by community of users	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Developing new features / functionality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The biggest financial burdens I face in using or developing software for my research are:

If you were given a budget of \$100 million to support research software development and maintenance in the USA how would you choose to spend it (i.e. to which types of activities would you allocate money and how much)? Please allocate your budget in millions of dollars. Responses need to total to \$100.

Project management	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Requirements elicitation / engineering	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Finding personnel	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Communication (among those with different expertise, among different teams)	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Use of best practices	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Rapid development	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Porting	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Testing	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Debugging	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Other <input type="text"/>	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Total	\$	<input type="text" value="0"/>

Career Path Follow Up

Do other members of your organization or institution use your software?

- Yes
 No
 Don't Know

Have other members of your organization contacted you about developing software for them?

- Yes

No

Rate the importance of each of the following factors when deciding upon accepting a new job position or promotion.

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Title of the position (e.g., junior research programmer vs. senior research programmer)	<input type="radio"/>				
Salary raise	<input type="radio"/>				
Responsibilities for a project or parts of a project	<input type="radio"/>				
Leading a team	<input type="radio"/>				
Available resources such as travel money	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

Credit for Software Follow Up

If you use open source software not developed by you, how important is the number of downloads for your decision to use it?

- Not at all important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Very important
- Extremely important
- N/A

If you use open source software not developed by you, how important is the number of contributors for your decision to use it?

- Not at all important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Very important
- Extremely important

N/A

If you use open source software not developed by you, how important is the presence of an academic publication about the software for your decision to use it?

- Not at all important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Very important
- Extremely important
- N/A

Diversity and Inclusion Follow Up

Considering the software project that you spend the most time working on, does this project have a diversity / inclusion statement or policy? If yes, please provide a link.

- Yes
- No, but we plan to develop one
- No, and we do not plan to develop one
- Other

You responded that the software project that you spend the most time working on has a diversity / inclusion statement or policy. In the box below, please provide a link to that statement or policy.

Considering the software project that you spend the most time working on or with, does this project have a code of conduct? If yes, please provide a link.

- Yes
- No, but we plan to develop one
- No, and we do not plan to develop one
- Other

You stated that the software project that you spend the most time working on or with has a code of conduct. In the box below, please provide a link to that code of conduct.

Which of the following inclusive practices and policies do you need support in creating for projects that focus on or include software development? Please mark all that apply.

- Recruiting diverse participants
- Retaining diverse participants
- Including diverse participants in governance and leadership positions
- Developing a code of conduct
- Developing a diversity / inclusivity policy

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